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TECHNICAL REPORT ON DESCRIPTION RULES FOR BRAZILIAN SIGN LANGUAGE

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1 Scope

This report presents a set of description rules for Brazilian Sign Language (Libras) to be used in the construction of a bilingual Brazilian Portuguese–Libras text corpus.

2 Description Rules for Brazilian Sign Language (Libras)

With the advancement of machine translation technologies and the understanding that their primary goal is to facilitate communication—thereby improving interaction, social inclusion, and the independence of deaf individuals—this technical report aims to contribute to the development of a set of description rules for a language that will support the construction of a bilingual Brazilian Portuguese–Libras text corpus, despite all the progress already made in the field of machine translation. Additionally, this report provides supporting information for the results achieved through automatic translation processes.

One of the main challenges in creating a Brazilian Portuguese–Libras corpus is the need to define a set of rules for writing signs in Libras, since statistical machine translation strategies typically require a written corpus in both the source and target languages. To address this issue, a set of rules was modeled and developed based on theoretical linguistic research in the related areas—Portuguese and Libras—aiming to represent Libras in written form through a gloss notation system.

3 Rules for Representing Glosses in Sign Languages

This section specifies the rules for representing glosses in sign language. These rules are necessary to specify grammatical aspects essential for sign languages and to allow for proper decoding of glosses in the sign language player.

It is essential to mention that these rules were developed for Brazilian Sign Language, but they are easily adaptable to any other sign language.

3.1 Homonyms and homographs

In this representation, words that have identical spelling in the written language (for example, Brazilian Portuguese) and different signs in the sign language, which are called homonyms, must receive a descriptive nomenclature at the end of the words, representing the context of the word. The character “&” shall be used to represent the disambiguation.

Tables 1 and 2 illustrate the homonyms COLAR and APAGAR in Brazilian Portuguese, and the variations in the Brazilian Sign Language using the proposed rule. Tables 3 and 4 illustrate some examples of glosses using these variations.

Table 1 - Homonyms COLAR and its variations in Brazilian Sign Language

HOMONYMS	VARIATIONS (GLOSS REPRESENTATION)	
COLAR	COLAR&ACESSÓRIO (NECKLACE&ACCESSORY)	COLAR&GRUDAR (PASTE&STICK)
	COLAR&FILAR (CHEAT&CHEAT)	COLAR&INFORMÁTICA (PASTE&INFORMATICS)

Tabela 2 - Homonyms APAGAR and its variations in Brazilian Sign Language

HOMÔNIMO	VARIÇÕES		
APAGAR	APAGAR&EXTINGUIR (DELETE&EXTINGUIS)	APAGAR&FOGO (PUT_OUT&FIRE)	APAGAR&INFORMÁTICA (DELETE&INFORMATICS)
	APAGAR&ESCREVER (ERASE&WRITE)	APAGAR&LOUSA (ERASE&BLACKBOARD)	APAGAR&LUZ (TURN_OFF&LIGHT)
	APAGAR&VELA (TURN_OFF&CANDLE)		

Table 3 - Examples of using the homonym COLAR and its variations.

SENTENÇA	REGRA APLICADA
Ganhei um colar da minha vó. (I got a necklace from my grandmother.)	GANHAR COLAR&ACESSÓRIO MEU VÓ [PONTO] (GET NECKLACE&ACCESSORY MY GRANDFATHER [PERIOD])
É errado colar na prova. (It's wrong to cheat on the test.)	ERRADO COLAR&FILAR PROVA [PONTO] WRONG CHEAT&CHEAT TEST [PERIOD]
O papel está todo colado. (The paper is all glued together.)	PAPEL COLAR&GRUDAR [PONTO] (PAPER PASTE&STICK [PERIOD])
Copie e cole o texto. (Copy and paste the text.)	COPIAR COLAR&INFORMÁTICA TEXTO [PONTO] (COPY PASTE&INFORMATICS TEXT [PERIOD])

Table 4 - Examples of using the homonym APAGAR and its variations.

INPUT SENTENCE	GLOSS REPRESENTATION
Cuidado, apague o fogo! (Be careful, put out the fire!)	CUIDADO APAGAR&FOGO [EXCLAMAÇÃO] (CAREFUL, PUT_OUT&FIRE [EXCLAMATION])

Apague essa sentença. (Delete this sentence.)	APAGAR&INFORMÁTICA SENTENÇA [PONTO] (DELETE&INFORMATICS SENTENCE [PERIOD])
Apague meu nome da lista. (Delete my name from the list.)	APAGAR&ESCREVER NOME LISTA[PONTO] (ERASE&WRITE NAME LIST [PERIOD])
Posso apagar o quadro? (Can I erase the painting?)	EU PODER APAGAR&LOUSA [INTERROGAÇÃO] (I CAN ERASE&BLACKBOARD [QUESTION])
Entre e apague a luz. (Come in and turn off the light.)	ENTRAR APAGAR&LUZ [PONTO] (COME IN TURN OFF&LIGHT)
Apague as velas e faça um pedido. (Extinguish the candles and make a wish.)	APAGAR&VELA FAZER PEDIDO&PEDIR [PONTO] (TURN_OFF&CANDLE MAKE ORDER&ORDER [PERIOD])

This rule enables correct translation considering the semantics and pragmatics of sign languages, as it allows the disambiguation of homonyms and homographs since, in the translation process, some signs may be more specific. Therefore, the translation must consider the meaning of the lexical item of the written language for a corresponding lexical item in sign language.

3.2 Punctuation marks

In the notation used for representing the sign language glosses, the punctuation identifying characters (“.”, “!” and “?”) shall be replaced by the spelling of the name in full between square brackets. Table 5 show.

Table 5 - Punctuation marks

PUNCTUATION MARK	GLOSS REPRESENTATION
Period: .	[PONTO] OR [PERIOD]
Exclamation Mark: !	[EXCLAMAÇÃO] OR [EXCLAMATION]
Question Mark: ?	[INTERROGAÇÃO] OR [INTERROGATION]

3.3 Adjectives: Unification of the gender of adjectives

In sign languages, adjectives are generally in the neutral form. Therefore, there is no marker for gender (masculine and feminine) nor for number (singular and plural) (BRITO, 2013, p. 63). Thus, in this gloss representation, the adjectives shall be inflected in the masculine to simplify the computational process.

Table 6 presents one example of the use of this rule involving adjectives.

Table 6 - Adjectives

INPUT SENTENCE	GLOSS REPRESENTATION
Essa flor é cheirosa! (This flower is smelly!)	ESSE FLOR CHEIROSO [EXCLAMAÇÃO] (THIS FLOWER SMELLY [EXCLAMATION])

3.4 Numerical Representations

In sign languages, there are different ways to present numerals when used as cardinals, ordinals, quantity, measurement, age, days of the week or month, hours, and monetary values. (FELIPE, 2007, p. 43). Concerning cardinal numbers, the rule is that the notation will always be in full and should not reference the digit (see Table 9). It is important to emphasize that the signing of the sentence presented in Table 7 will be done with the sign referring to the number 4, not its fingerspelling.

Table 7 - Cardinal Numbers

INPUT SENTENCE	GLOSS REPRESENTATION
Eu preciso comprar 4 cadernos. (I need to buy 4 notebooks.)	EU PRECISAR COMPRAR QUATRO CADERNO [PONTO] (I NEED TO BUY FOUR NOTEBOOKS [PERIOD])

Ordinal numbers are expressed in their full notation with the addition of the disambiguation identifier (“&”) to the ordinal numerals (from the first to the fifth number) since they are homonymous words in some written languages (e.g., Brazilian Portuguese). Table 8 shows the application of the rule for ordinal numbers.

Table 8 - Ordinal numbers

SYMBOL	GLOSS REPRESENTATION
1°	PRIMEIRO&ORDINAL (FIRST&ORDINAL)
2°	SEGUNDO&ORDINAL (SECOND&ORDINAL)
3°	TERCEIRO&ORDINAL (THIRD&ORDINAL)
4°	QUARTO&ORDINAL (FOURTH&ORDINAL)
5°	QUINTO&ORDINAL (FIFTH&ORDINAL)
6°	SEXTO (SIXTH)
7°	SÉTIMO (SEVENTH)
8°	OITAVO (EIGHTH)
9°	NONO (NINETH)
10°	DÉCIMO (TENTH)
11°	DÉCIMO PRIMEIRO&ORDINAL (ELEVENTH&ORDINAL)
12°	DÉCIMO SEGUNDO&ORDINAL (TWELFTH&ORDINAL)
20°	VIGÉSIMO (TWENTIETH)

When a number refers to a quantity, specific signs must be used in sign language. Regarding time, for example, there are two different ways of referring to time in sign languages: chronological or duration (FELIPE, 2007, p. 78). Thus, specific signs must be used for duration. Thus, it is possible to disambiguate the numeral, differentiating a quantitative numeral from a representative one (see Table 9).

Table 9 - Numbers and quantity

INPUT	GLOSS REPRESENTATION
1 hora (1 hour)	UM_HORA (ONE_HOUR)
1 pessoa	UM_PESSOA

(1 person)

(ONE_PERSON)

To represent time, common abbreviations present in written languages must be treated and described using the “HORA” (HOUR), “MINUTO” (MINUTE), “SEGUNDO” (SECOND), “MANHÃ” (MORNING), “TARDE” (AFTERNOON) and “NOITE” (NIGHT) glosses, among others. Table 10 presents two examples of time treatment in gloss.

Tabela 10 - Time period

INPUT SENTENCE	GLOSS REPRESENTAION
São 3h30. (It is 3:30 am.)	TRÊS HORA TRINTA MINUTO MANHÃ [PONTO] (THREE HOUR THIRTY MINUTE MORNING [PERIOD])
A reunião será às 14h30. (The meeting will be at 2:30 pm.)	REUNIÃO DOIS HORA TRINTA MINUTO TARDE [PONTO] (MEETING TWO HOUR THIRTY MINUTES AFTERNOON [PERIOD])

It is also common in sign languages to have a different numerical representation for fractions, percentages, and currency. In this notation, the following representation will be adopted:

- **Fraction:** The fraction symbol will be replaced by the “FRAÇÃO” (FRACTION) gloss;
- **Percentage:** The percentage symbol % will be replaced by the “PORCENTAGEM” (PERCENTAGE) gloss;
- **Games or disputes:** The X symbol will be replaced by the “VERSUS” (VERSUS) gloss;
- **Currencies:** The currency symbol will be replaced by its full representation of the currency (e.g.: R\$ -> “REAL&MOEDA” (REAL&COIN) and US\$ = “DOLLAR”).

Table 11 presents some examples of usage involving these numerical representations.

Tabela 11 - Examples of different numerical representations

INPUT SENTENCE	GLOSS REPRESENTATION
Temos $\frac{2}{3}$ de aprovação. (We have $\frac{2}{3}$ approval.)	TER DOIS FRAÇÃO TRÊS APROVAR [PONTO] (WE HAVE TWO FRACTION THREE APPROVE [PERIOD])
A música teve 25,5% de rejeição. (The song had 25.5% rejection.)	MÚSICA TER VINTE E CINCO VÍRGULA CINCO PORCENTAGEM REJEIÇÃO [PONTO] (MUSIC HAVE TWENTY FIVE COMMA FIVE PERCENTAGE REJECTION [PERIOD])
Fluminense ganhou de 4x2 do Vasco. (Fluminense won 4x2 against Vasco.)	FLUMINENSE GANHAR QUATRO VERSUS DOIS VASCO [PONTO] (FLUMINENSE WIN FOUR VERSUS TWO VASCO [PERIOD])
Eu preciso de R\$ 4,99. (I need R\$4.99.)	EU PRECISAR QUATRO REAL&MOEDA NOVENTA E NOVE CENTAVOS [PONTO] (I NEED FOUR REAL&COIN NINETY-NINE CENTS [PERIOD])

3.5 Compound words

Compound words or expressions represented by a single sign must be separated by _ (underscore). For some words, it is important to mention that words in written languages are composed of more than one element. However, when in sign languages, they are considered as simple signs. (NASCIMENTO, 2011,

p. 52). As a rule, this notation will also be applied to greetings which are represented as a simple sign (see Table 12).

Tabela 12 - Compound words

INPUT	GLOSS REPRESENTATION
Comprei um novo guarda-roupa. (I bought a new wardrobe.)	COMPRAR GUARDA_ROUPA NOVO [PONTO] (BUY NEW WARDROBE [PERIOD])
Bom dia! (Good morning!)	BOM_DIA [EXCLAMAÇÃO] (GOOD_MORNING [EXCLAMATION])
Boa tarde! (Good afternoon!)	BOA_TARDE [EXCLAMAÇÃO] (GOOD_AFTERNOON!)
Boa noite! (Good Night!)	BOA_NOITE [EXCLAMAÇÃO] (GOOD_NIGHT [EXCLAMATION])

3.6 Directional Verbs

In directional verbs (or verbs with gender agreement for the person) in sign languages, the agreement between sender and receiver must be respected. In this sense, the notation of verbs in their infinitive form receives the characters *S (“*” identifies the number and “S” identifies the singular) or *P (“*” identifies the number and “P” identifies the plural), as nomenclatures of direction. Thus, we have the following representation for personal pronouns:

- EU (I) => 1S;
- TU/VOCÊ (YOU) => 2S;
- ELE/ELA (HE/SHE) => 3S;
- NÓS (WE) => 1P;
- VÓS/VOCÊS (YOU) => 2P;
- ELES/ELAS (THEY) => 3P.

Tables 13 present examples of the treatment of verbs with gender agreement in the singular and plural, respectively.

Table 13 - Examples of using verbs with number-person agreement

INPUT SENTENCE	GLOSS REPRESENTATION
Eu perguntei a sua idade. (I asked your age.)	1S_PERGUNTAR_2S IDADE [PONTO] (1S ASK 2S AGE [PERIOD])
O que você me perguntou? (What did you ask me?)	2S_PERGUNTAR_1S QUE [INTERROGAÇÃO] (2S ASK 1S WHAT [QUESTION])
Ela perguntou meu nome. (She asked my name.)	3S_PERGUNTAR_1S NOME [PONTO] (3S ASK 1S NAME [PERIOD])
Ele perguntou a ela sua idade. (He asked her age.)	3S_PERGUNTAR_3S IDADE [PONTO] (3S ASK 3S AGE [PERIOD])
Nós perguntamos a sua idade. (We asked your age.)	1P_PERGUNTAR_2S IDADE [PONTO] (1P ASK 2S AGE [PERIOD])
Vocês perguntam a minha idade. (You ask my age.)	2P_PERGUNTAR_1S IDADE [PONTO] (2P ASK 1S AGE [PERIOD])
Eles perguntaram a sua idade. (They asked your age.)	3P_PERGUNTAR_2S IDADE [PONTO] (3P ASK 2S AGE [PERIOD])

3.7 Incorporation of Negation

The incorporation of negation initially applies to verbs when the negation adverb is modified in the direct or indirect object. In this case, it is possible to simplify by saying that if the NEGATION signing can be done simultaneously with a word (verb), this specific rule must be applied. In negative sentences, the movement of the head (denying) and facial expressions are mandatory to mark negative sentences, as they are directly linked to syntactic issues; otherwise, the sentence will become ungrammatical. (ALMEIDA; ALMEIDA, 2012, p. 628).

In this gloss notation, the incorporation of negation is done by incorporating the prefix “NÃO_” (NOT_) into the sign, to facilitate the reading of the description. Table 14 presents two examples of the application of this rule.

Tabela 14 - Examples of using incorporation of negation

INPUT SENTENCE	GLOSS REPRESENTATION
Eu não posso mais esperar. (I can't wait anymore.)	EU NÃO_PODER ESPERAR [PONTO] (I NOT CAN WAIT [PERIOD])
Ele não consegue ganhar. (He can't win.)	ELE NÃO_CONSEGUIR GANHAR [PONTO] (HE NOT_CAN WIN [POINT])

3.8 Amplification and reduction of intensity

Intensifiers are used when the word, verb or expression is close to some adverb of intensity. This intensity is characterized by the sign's duration, energy, variance, and average speed (PASSOS, 2014, p.19). In this representation, the markers "(+)" or "(-)" should be inserted at the end of the word to represent the intensifier. In this case, the adverbs of intensity "muito" (very), "mais" (more), "muitíssimo" (very much) and their synonyms will be represented by the marker "(+)" at the end of the word. In contrast, the adverbs "pouco" (little), "menos" (less), "pouquíssimo" (very little) and their synonyms will be represented by the marker "(-)" at the end of the word.

Table 15 presents some examples of the application of the rule in sentences with increased and reduced intensity.

Tabela 15 -Examples of using amplification and reduction of intensity

INPUT SENTENCE	REGRA APLICADA
Ele está muito deprimido. (He is very depressed.)	ELE DEPRIMIDO(+) [PONTO] (HE DEPRESSED(+) [PERIOD])
Ela é tão bonita! (She is so pretty!)	ELE BONITO(+) [EXCLAMAÇÃO] (HE BEAUTIFUL(+) [EXCLAMATION])
Você está nervoso demais. (You are too nervous.)	VOCÊ NERVOSO(+) [PONTO] (YOU NERVOUS(+) [PERIOD])
Estou um pouco doente. (I am a little sick.)	EU DOENTE(-) [PONTO] (I SICK(-) [DOT])